

Molecular Sorption on Ion Exchange Resins: Effect of Solvent and of Solute Structure

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The effect of the solvent and of the solute structure on the sorption equilibrium and on column elution runs for cation exchange resins has been studied. Based on these studies, two and three component mixtures have been separated.

Earlier,¹⁻³ the sorption of some mono and dicarboxylic acids with sulphonic and carboxylic acid cation exchange resins had been studied. Here, the effect of the solvent and of the solute structure on the sorption equilibrium and column elution runs for cation exchange resins has been studied at room temperature ($\sim 30^\circ$). Based on these studies, two and three component mixtures have been separated.

EXPERIMENTAL

*Resins*¹⁻³ were from stocks used in earlier work. These included :

(a) *Dowex 50W* (Dow Chemical Co.) styrene divinylbenzene copolymer based sulphonic acid cation exchange resins of relative degree of crosslinking (% nominal divinylbenzene content) X=4, 8 and 12 (further referred to as resins X 4, X8 and X 12) the resins were conditioned and regenerated into hydrogen form. The percent moisture and the capacity in meq. per oven dry gram were : X 4, 29.9, 5.06; X 8, 27.6, 4.89; X 12, 27.1, 4.85.

(b) *Zeo-Karb 226* (Permutit Co.) Carboxylic acid cation exchange resins of relative degree of crosslinking (% nominal divinylbenzene content) X=2.5, 5, 10 and 15 (further referred to as resins CX 2.5, CX 5, CX 10 and CX 15) of -40, +60 mesh ; these are presumably based on acrylic acid divinylbenzene copolymers. The resins were conditioned and regenerated into hydrogen form. The percent moisture and the capacity in meq. per oven dry gram were: CX 2.5, 23.4, 10.50 ; CX 5, 20.9, 9.95; CX10, 17.0 8.78; CX 15, 12.0, 6.95.

(c) *Amberlite IRC-50* (Rohm and Haas Co.) of -40, +60 mesh (further referred to as resin IRC-50); this is presumably methacrylic acid divinylbenzene copolymer based carboxylic acid cation exchange resin. The resin was conditioned and regenerated into hydrogen form. The percent moisture and the capacity in meq. per oven dry gram were : 15.6, 10.30.

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Chemicals were of A. R. or C. P. grade. Aqueous pyruvic acid was prepared by passing a small quantity of the aqueous solution of its sodium salt through a column of the sulphonic acid cation exchange resin X4 in hydrogen form, followed by washing out the column with water.

The procedure for sorption equilibrium study was similar to that given earlier¹. Phenol was estimated by bromination method and the rest were estimated by titration against standard sodium hydroxide solution.

Aqueous acetone and aqueous dioxan were prepared by volume. The dielectric constant for the mixed solvent was measured on Multi-Dekameter-Type DK 06 (WTW) using 1.8 m/cs frequency at room temperature.

For column runs, column B and C, containing the sulphonic acid cation exchange resin (X4 described earlier³) were used and the procedure followed was similar. The column data were as follows :

Column	B	C
Resin	X4 (-100,+200)	X4 (-50,+100)
Bed length (cm.)	94	210
Bed volume (ml.)	220	490
Capacity of the resin in column (meq.)	283	628
Flow rate of effluent (ml./min.)	2	2

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Sorption equilibrium studies : The sorption equilibrium of n-butyric acid and iso-butyric acid with sulphonic acid cation exchange resin, X4 and carboxylic acid cation exchange resin, IRC-50 in aqueous acetone and aqueous dioxan was studied. Preliminary work had indicated that small variation in temperature did not make significant change. The values¹⁻³ of S were calculated from $S = (C_o - C_e) / C_r$, where C_o and C_e are the initial and equilibrium concentration of solute in gram equivalents per liter, and C_r is the capacity of air dry resin in equivalents added per liter of solution, and then S was plotted against C_e . The plots were linear and the slope of such plots is termed as B. The values of B, thus obtained, are plotted against the dielectric constant, D of the mixed solvent used (Figures 1 and 2). It is observed that the values of B for each acid-resin pair may be considered to fall on a single curve for the mixed solvents used, implying the dependence of B on D. This may be attributed to the dependence of the dipole-dipole interactions on the dielectric constant. The value of B for the iso-acid is less than that for n-acid in the mixed solvent for both sulphonic and carboxylic acid type resins.

The sorption of benzoic acid and some substituted benzoic acids was studied with sulphonic acid cation exchange resins X4, X8 and X12. The values of B were obtained, as before, from the slopes of the linear plots of S against C_e and are given in Table I. It follows that for sulphonic acid cation exchange resins studied, the amount of acid sorbed per unit capacity of the resin is directly proportional to the equilibrium concentration of the acid and inversely proportional to the degree of crosslinking of the resin. The sorption of nitrobenzoic acid was also studied on resin X16, (having degree of crosslinking=16) and the value of $B=0.9$ is thus inversely proportional to X. These conclusions are similar to those for sorption of aliphatic monocarboxylic acids on these resins¹. The comparison of the values of B for benzoic acid and the straight chain n-heptylic acid (both containing 7

carbon atoms) indicates that the value for benzoic acid is more than that for n-heptylic acid. Further the hydroxyl group in the ring of benzoic acid reduces the value of B, that is the sorption of the acid. The nitro group in meta position in the ring of benzoic acid increases the value of B. When the carboxyl group of benzoic acid is replaced by hydroxyl group, that is for phenol the sorption observed is lower.

FIG. 1 Variation of B with D, for (1) n-butyric acid and (2) iso-butyric acid with the resin X4 in, ● water, ⊙ aqueous acetone and ■ aqueous dioxan.

FIG. 2. Variation of B with D, for (1) n-butyric acid and (2) iso-butyric acid with resin IRC-50 in, ● water, ⊙ aqueous acetone and ■ aqueous dioxan.

Sorption equilibrium of benzoic acid and phenol was also studied with carboxylic acid cation exchange resins CX 2.5, CX 5, CX 10, CX 15 and IRC-50 and the values of B obtained from the linear plot of S against C_e , are given in Table II. Again the replacement of carboxyl group by hydroxyl group in benzoic acid decreases the value of B. The value of B for each first increases and then decreases as the degree of crosslinking increases from 2.5 to 15. This behaviour is similar to that observed for aliphatic monocarboxylic acids with these resins.²

TABLE I

Values of B for sulphonic acid cation exchange resins.

Acid	10 B for Resin		
	X4	X8	XI2
Benzoic	26.8	13.4	8.0
<i>o</i> -Hydroxy benzoic	21.2	10.6	7.2
<i>p</i> -Hydroxy benzoic	21.2	10.0	7.0
<i>m</i> -Hydroxy benzoic	12.0	6.0	3.6
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic	35.5	17.5	11.6
Phenol	12.6	6.3	4.2

TABLE II

Values of B for carboxylic acid cation exchange resins

	10 B for Resin				
	CX 2.5	CX 5	CX10	CX 15	IRC-50
Benzoic acid	10.3	21.2	24.2	3.8	13.6
Phenol	3.3	5.1	6.7	3.0	2.7

Column studies : The column elution runs for some unsaturated, α -keto and some hydroxy acids were carried out on column C and Table III gives the results with water as the solvent and eluant. It is observed that for the *cis* and *trans* isomers, maleic acid and fumaric acid, the elution runs differ and these also differ from that for the corresponding saturated acid, succinic acid³. The presence of the double bond in the acid molecule appears to reduce the sorption to a greater extent for the *cis* than for the *trans* form.

The runs for α -keto acids (Table III) suggest that α -keto group in the acid molecule reduces the sorption when compared with that for the parent acid³ and that α -keto acid could be separated from its parent acid with water as solvent and eluant. Figures 3 and 4 give the separation of pyruvic acid from propionic acid and of α -ketoglutaric acid from glutaric acid with water as solvent and eluant.

TABLE III

Elution of carboxylic acids on column³ C with water

Acid= 10 ² .W= Sample No. (each=25 cc.)	maleic 131	fumaric 124	lactic 133	malic 127	tartaric 122	pyruvic 105	α -ketoglutaric 108
v.v.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
1-2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
3	2.5	—	—	—	—	1.9	0.6
4	10.3	—	—	0.4	0.5	5.3	4.0
5	23.2	—	—	0.7	2.4	6.3	10.2
6	47.0	1.0	0.7	2.1	10.1	7.9	22.6
7	47.0	1.8	1.5	7.9	38.2	17.8	44.9
8	1.2	3.0	2.1	32.3	62.2	38.2	25.9
9	—	5.7	5.0	62.5	8.7	27.2	0.2
10	—	10.0	16.4	20.9	—	0.5	—
11	—	18.0	48.5	0.4	—	—	—
12	—	31.2	51.6	—	—	—	—
13	—	38.8	7.4	—	—	—	—
14	—	14.2	—	—	—	—	—
15	—	0.5	—	—	—	—	—
16	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

When the elution runs for hydroxy acids given in Table III are compared with those for the parent acids,³ it is indicated that a hydroxyl group in the molecule of the carboxylic acids studied reduces the sorption to some extent; the second hydroxyl group further reduces the sorption, but relatively to a lesser extent.

FIG. 3. Separation of pyruvic acid (10^2 . $W=55.6$) from propionic acid (10^2 . $W=58.1$) on column C with water as solvent and eluant.

FIG. 4. Separation of α -ketoglutaric acid (10^2 . $W=56.3$) from glutaric acid (10^2 . $W=61.6$) on column C with water as solvent and eluant.

The column elution of phthalic, phenylacetic and benzoic acid was also studied³ on column C containing resin X4. This indicated that phthalic, phenylacetic and benzoic acid could be separated in a mixture with water as solvent and eluant, but the elution of these acids was slow. With the use of aqueous acetone as a solvent and eluant in place of water for the entire run, these acids could be eluted and separated relatively faster and in a lesser number of samples. Figure 5 gives the separation of phthalic, phenylacetic and benzoic acids on column C with 10% (by volume) aqueous acetone as solvent and eluant. The procedure for this run was as follows: The solutions of organic acids were prepared in 10% aqueous acetone and the mixture prepared by mixing them in known amounts. The column C was rinsed with several bed volumes of 10% aqueous acetone and the sorption and elution were carried out as before using 10% aqueous acetone as eluant.

The comparison of the elution runs (Table III and figure 5) supports the conclusions that the introduction of a second carboxyl group in the molecule of a monocarboxylic acid reduces the sorption³.

FIG. 5. Separation of phthalic acid (10^2 . $W=34.2$), phenylacetic acid (10^2 . $W=35.9$) and benzoic acid (10^2 . $W=33.4$) on column C with 10% (by volume) aqueous acetone³ as solvent and eluant.

The elution run for naphthalene-2-sulphonic (NF) acid on column B containing resin X4 was obtained and then compared with those for aliphatic monocarboxylic acids³. It is suggested that NF acid can be separated from the latter. In binary mixture, NF acid was

first eluted with water as eluant and then the carboxylic acid was eluted with water or aqueous acetone. The advantage in using aqueous acetone was that the longer chain carboxylic acid could be eluted faster and in lesser number of samples than when water was used as eluant. Three typical runs are given in Tables IV and V to illustrate the type of results obtained. Table IV gives the separation of NF acid from acetic acid on column B

TABLE IV

Separation of naphthalene-2-sulphonic acid from acetic acid

Acid= 10 ² W=	NF acid [25.9 + in 10 cc. aqueous mixture]	+	Acetic acid 25.0]
Sample No. (each=10 cc.)	10 ² Ws=		
1-7	—		—
8	0.3		—
9	6.1		—
10	13.1		—
11	6.2		—
12	0.2		—
13-16	—		—
17	—		0.6
18	—		6.9
19	—		13.3
20	—		4.1
21	—		0.1
22	—		—

TABLE V

Separation of naphthalene-2-sulphonic acid from n-caproic acid

Acid= 10 ² W=	run a			run b		
	NF acid [64.6 + in 25 cc. mixture]	+	n-caproic acid 54.6]	NF acid [64.6 + in 25 cc. mixture]	+	n-caproic acid 54.6]
Sample No. (each=25 cc)	10 ² Ws=			10 ² Ws=		
1-3	—		—	—		—
4	22.1		—	22.1		—
5	41.8		—	41.8		—
6	0.7		—	0.7		—
7	—		—	—	A.A.	—
8-14	—		—	—		—
15	—		—	—		21.1
16	—		—	—		33.2
17	—		—	—		0.3
18	—		2.0	—		—
19	—		11.1	—		—
20	—		23.9	—		—
21	—		14.7	—		—
22	—		2.6	—		—
23	—		0.3	—		—
24	—		—	—		—

A. A. means that the eluant after this sample was 25% aqueous acetone.

using water as solvent and eluant. Table V gives the separation of NF acid from n-caproic acid on the same column; in run (a) the eluant was water and in the run (b) the eluant was water upto sample number 7 and after this the eluant was 25% (by volume) aqueous acetone. Comparison of runs (a) and (b) in Table V indicates that a aqueous acetone may be preferred to elute the second component.

Symbols used : W = the acid content, meq., in the volume of the acid solution taken and sorbed on the resin bed. The volume of the acid solution taken was 10 cc. for the run given in Table IV; for all the other runs given, it was 25 cc.

W_s = the acid content, meq., in each effluent sample. In the run given in Table IV, the effluent sample volume was 10 cc., in all other runs given, the sample volume was 25 cc. other symbols used are same as given before.¹⁻³

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